

AWARENESS AND KNOWLEDGE OF NURSING CARE IN EAR, NOSE AND THROAT DISORDERS

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ABSTRACT

Diseases of the ear, nose and throat (ENT) are universally a significant general health concern. The Global Burden of Disease (GBD), including ENT conditions, has consistently been accounted for to be relative to asset deprivation. This study aimed to analyse the nursing care in ear, nose and throat disorders in a tertiary care hospital of China. This prospective cross sectional study was done in DHQ teaching Hospital Sargodha during June 2018 to June 2019. This study provides the data related to nursing care of ENT disorder in Pakistan. The data was collected through a questionnaire. The data was collected from those patients who visited the hospital for ENT disorders. The data collection team consist of ENT specialists, audiologists and hospital nurses. The hospital was well equipped with an operating microscope and ENT instruments. The data was collected from 100 patients which were appropriate for our inclusion criteria. We observe all the symptoms that were commonly present in patients. So that we can identify the care related to these symptoms and problems of ENT. According to our results the group B which were handled with trained nurses for ENT nursing care were showed the better results as compared to group A who have less knowledge of nursing care. It is concluded that creating awareness of the common ENT conditions and how they are caused and treatment options available help decrease the burden of the disease in the community.

Keywords: ENT, nursing, care, hospitals, disorders.

INTRODUCTION

Diseases of the ear, nose and throat (ENT) are universally a significant general health concern. The Global Burden of Disease (GBD), including ENT conditions, has consistently been accounted for to be relative to asset deprivation. Despite the fact that created nations are not exclude from the high ENT malady trouble, low pay African and Asian nations are generally influenced (Jacoby *et al.*, 2008). All around, incapacitating hearing misfortune influences around 466 million individuals, weakening individual sufferers, families and nations the same. Head and neck cancer, the ninth most normal harm, has high death rates in creating nations. In

most of spots, people with correspondence troubles are not organized in health care frameworks as government's center around sparing lives rather than improving personal satisfaction (Sauer *et al.*, 2000).

Numerous patients with states of the ear, nose, and throat report a scope of various side effects and expectation their internist can recommend a cure that will lighten their wretchedness and cause them to feel better rapidly (Straetemans *et al.*, 2003). The most widely recognized ENT states of sinusitis, hearing misfortune, vertigo, and tinnitus can be assessed and treated in the essential care office, however indications of an intense or extreme condition should provoke a referral to

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a subspecialist, specialists concurred (Sullivan *et al.*, 2001).

The most well-known issues justifying a visit to a specialist or a health care supplier in creating nations are related to ear nose and throat (ENT). ENT issues are the most widely recognized issues for which there are home solutions for medical treatments which are accessible, and most people deal with their concern in the network without looking for help (Malone *et al.*, 1997). What's more, because of the absence of authority experts right now, issues are treated by network rehearses. The investigations done have taken a gander at the commonness of ENT illnesses in kids and have indicated that the infection trouble is because of otitis media and its sequelae which are the most well-known reasons for preventable hearing misfortune in kids in creating nations (Ahmadiashar *et al.*, 2012).

The prevalence of traditional practices increased the disease morbidity requiring surgical management. Postal review utilizing survey techniques was utilized to evaluate the commonness of ENT-related issue in a network (Greenberg and Pinto 2003). There is no data on the commonness of otorhinolaryngological illnesses in a rustic network in India. The present examination was embraced to decide the commonness of ENT issue in population presenting to an auxiliary care emergency clinic with accentuation on essential care in country networks and innate territory (Yeung-Yue *et al.*, 2002).

A few issues of the ear, nose and throat (ENT) are normal; the vast majority sooner or later in their lives experience the ill effects of nosebleeds, sore throats or ear infection. A large number of these issues will be managed effectively at home, regularly with the exhortation of a drug specialist or general expert (GP) (Pathak *et al.*, 2007). Some ENT issues, in any case, can be perilous, requiring a quick visit to a crisis department (ED), medical procedure and, sometimes, a time of

nursing care at home after release (Sanders *et al.*, 2009).

To nurse ENT patients effectively in a home or emergency clinic setting, a fundamental information on the life structures and physiology of the applicable structures, alongside an exhaustive understanding of the clinical highlights of normal issue, is essential (WHO 2012). The health guest, network nurse, school nurse or word related health nurse is regularly in a situation to recognize issues before the medical specialist or even the patient knows about them (Emerson *et al.*, 2013).

This study aimed to analyse the nursing care in ear, nose and throat disorders in a tertiary care hospital of China.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This prospective cross sectional study was done in DHQ teaching Hospital Sargodha during June 2018 to June 2019. This study provides the data related to nursing care of ENT disorder in Pakistan.

Inclusion criteria

- All those patients who were suffered from any kind of ENT disorder were included in this study.

Exclusion criteria

- Those patients who were suffering from any other issue, for example CVD were not included in this study.
- Those who have major surgeries were also not included in this study.

Study design

We divided this study into two groups, Group A and Group B.

Group A: Patients were handled with non-trained staff and nurses for ENT care.

Group B: Patients were handled with trained staff and nurses for nursing care of ENT disorders.

Data collection

The data was collected through a questionnaire. The data was collected from those patients who visited the hospital for ENT disorders. The data collection team consist of ENT specialists, audiologists and hospital nurses. The hospital was well equipped with an operating microscope and ENT instruments. The hospital staff and nurses were taught about safe ear care practices, the harmful effects of prevalent traditional practices, and the treatment options available. They know how to identify the ENT disorders e.g. ear pain with or without discharge, sour throat, respiratory tract infection, throat pain, swelling, difficulty in eating and fever. The age range for this study was 10 to 50 years. Questionnaire method of data collection was used to know the prevalence of ENT-related conditions and analysing the nursing care in ENT disorders. This questionnaire include all the questions related to nursing care of ENT disorders.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

All data were displayed in mean ± SD and analysed through SPSS 19.0 (IBM, USA). T-test and one-way ANOVA were applied for measuring comparison among groups. P<0.05 was considered to have statistical meaning.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data was collected from 100 patients

which were appropriate for our inclusion criteria. We observe all the symptoms that were commonly present in patients. So that we can identify the care related to these symptoms and problems of ENT. According to our results the group B which were handled with trained nurses for ENT nursing care were showed the better results as compared to group A who have less knowledge of nursing care. Subsequent to preparing, the mean score for the test in the gathering B expanded to 68%, demonstrating a measurably huge improvement from benchmark (p<0.001). There was additionally upgrades in information for the individual modules, and appraisal and directing.

The majority of the nurses (77%) said that the length of the training was right, whereas 23% thought that it was too short. In dealing with patients with ENT disorders, 62% reported that they felt comfortable and 38% felt very comfortable after the training. None of the nurses reported feeling uncomfortable in this study.

According to our results 60% of the patients showed pain and discharge in throat disorders, 29% ear and 11% nose disorders.

There is need to accomplish more research on the arrangement of demonstrative and helpful PEHC benefits by CHWs and general health workers at bleeding edge health offices. With the approach of a lot of

Table 1
Analysis of questionnaire of nursing care in ENT disorders

Module	Analysis of questionnaire		Significance
	Group A	Group B	
Structure and function of the ear	56%	61%	<0.0001
Hearing impairment and deafness: causes and prevention	51%	53%	<0.0001
The outer ear: examine, treat and refer	52%	63%	<0.0001
The ear canal: examine, diagnose and clean	51%	67%	0.03
The middle ear: examine, diagnose and treat	50%	58%	0.28
Assessing hearing and counselling	62%	79%	0.17
All modules	48%	65%	<0.0001

Fig. A - represents the frequency of ENT disorders and Fig. B - present the views of patients related to nursing care in Group A and Group B nursing group. It showed that group B express more nursing care in ENT disorders.

Fig. 1: ROC curve of group A before training of nurses for care in ENT disorders

Fig. 2: ROC curve of group B presents after training of nurses for care in ENT disorders.

programming applications for audiometry, there is needed to look at the feasibility of outfitting the CHWs with the gadget (Berg *et al.*, 2006). Moreover, research is needed concerning which helpful methodologies are proper at the essential level. For example, essential healthcare laborers are frequently

educated to do dry cleaning for wet holes. Among our patients with wet holes, various them had dead house flies in the ears which may have been hard to expel with dry wiping alone (Mulwafu *et al.*, 2014). Proof is additionally needed regarding whether ear

syringing might be valuable for these kinds of conditions (Tataryn *et al.*, 2013).

ENT ailments keep on pulling in little attention notwithstanding being a significant reason for dismalness and mortality around the world. Past examinations have consistently detailed under-resourced, understaffed and obsolete ENT, audiology and language instruction benefits in most of low pay nations (Makaula *et al.*, 2012). With practically all the center ENT and supporting health staff situated in Lusaka city, the remainder of the nation's ENT administration is insignificant, and in numerous spots, non-existent. Therefore, emergency clinics offering ENT administrations are overpowered with patients as are numerous more significant level medical clinics in creating nations (Tong *et al.*, 2007).

The enormous patient burden unavoidably prompts less medical experts and nursing staff, with quick consumption of the accessible assets (Kalua *et al.*, 2012; Kyabayinze *et al.*, 2012; Müller *et al.*, 2010). Thus, patient dreariness and mortality increments due to imperfect handling of medical and careful crises, poor nursing care, absence of basic care beds and careful blunder exuding from health specialist fatigue (Mulwafu *et al.*, 2016).

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that creating awareness of the common ENT conditions and how they are caused and treatment options available help decrease the burden of the disease in the community. Utilizing prepared nursing care staff to spread the message of safe ENT rehearses, gives restoration of hearing misfortune through arrangement of hearing guides, and the assessment and careful administration by the pro (when seven days) helped the provincial network to get to the administration.

REFERENCES

Acuin MA (2012). Addressing ear and hearing problems at primary level. *Community Ear and Hearing Health*, **9**: 1-2.

Ahmadiafshar A, Farjd HR, Moezzi F and Mousavinasab N (2012). Nasal polyposis in patients with asthma and allergic rhinitis. *J. Laryngol. Otol.*, **126**(8): 780-783.

Berg AL, Papri H, Ferdous S, Khan NZ and Durkin MS (2006). Screening methods for childhood hearing impairment in rural Bangladesh. *Int. J. Pediatr. Otorhinolaryngol.*, **70**: 107-114.

Elsbury D, Stokes A, Monck R, Finucane JM, Emerson LP, Job A and Abraham V (2013). A model for provision of ENT health care service at primary and secondary hospital level in a developing country. *Biomed. Res. Int.*, **2013**: 1-5.

Fagan JJ and Jacobs M (2009). Survey of ENT services in Africa: Need for a comprehensive intervention. *Glob. Health Action*, **2**: 1932

Grace Bongololo Mbera GB, Mangani C, de Sousa A, Nkhono E, Jemu S, and Muula AS (2012). Primary health care in rural Malawi – a qualitative assessment exploring the relevance of the community-directed interventions approach. *BMC Health Serv. Res.*, **12**: 328.

Greenberg MS and Pinto A (2003). Etiology and management of recurrent aphthous stomatitis. *Curr. Infect. Dis. Rep.*, **5**(3): 194-198.

Khumbo Kalua K, Ruby Tionenji Ng'ongola RT, Frank Mbewe F and Gilbert C (2012). Using primary health care (PHC) workers and key informants for community based detection of blindness in children in Southern Malawi. *Hum. Resour. Health*, **10**: 37.

Kyabayinze DJ, Asiiimwe C, Nakanjako D and Nabakooza J, Bajabaite M, Strachan C, Tibenderana JK and Van Geetruyden JPV (2012). Programme level implementation of malaria rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) use: outcomes and cost of training health workers at lower level health care facilities in Uganda. *BMC Public Health*, **12**: 291

Malone DC, Lawson KA, Smith DH, Arrighi HM and Battista C (1997). A cost of illness study of allergic rhinitis in the

- United States. *J. Allergy Clin. Immunol.*, **99**(1): 22-27.
- Müller A, Murenzi J, Mathenge W, Munana J and Courtright P (2010). Primary eye care in Rwanda: gender of service providers and other factors associated with effective service delivery. *Trop. Med. Int. Health*, **15**: 529-533.
- Mulwafu W, Kuper H and Ensink RJ (2016). Prevalence and causes of hearing impairment in Africa. *Trop. Med. Int. Health*, **21**: 158-165.
- Mulwafu W, Nyirenda TE, Fagan JJ, Bem C, Kumvana Mlumbe K and Chitule J (2014). Initiating and developing clinical services, training and research in a low resource setting: the Malawi ENT experience. *Trop. Doct.*, **44**: 135-139.
- Pathak P, Kapil U, Yajnik CS, Kapoor SK, Dwivedi SN and Singh R (2007). Iron, folate, and vitamin B12 stores among pregnant women in a rural area of Haryana State, India. *Food Nutr. Bull.*, **28**(4): 435-438.
- Sanders M, Houghton N, Dewes O and McCool J and Thorne PR (2015). Estimated prevalence of hearing loss and provision of hearing services in Pacific Island nations. *J. Prim. Health Care*, **7**: 5-15.
- St Sauver J, Marrs CF, Foxman B, Somsel P, Madera R and Gilsdorf JR (2000). Risk factors for otitis media and carriage of multiple strains of *Haemophilus influenzae* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. *Emerg. Infect. Dis.*, **6**(6): 622-630.
- Straetemans M, Sanders EAM, Veenhoven RH, Schilder AGM, Damoiseaux RAMJ and Zielhuis GA (2003). Review of randomized controlled trials on pneumococcal vaccination for prevention of otitis media. *Pediatr. Infect. Dis. J.*, **22**(6): 515-524.
- Sullivan SD and Weiss KB (2001). Health economics of asthma and rhinitis — II. Assessing the value of interventions. *J. Allergy Clin. Immunol.*, **107**(2): 203-210.
- Tataryn M, Chokotho L, Mulwafu W, Kayange P, Polack S, Lavy C and Kuper H (2013). Malawi key informant disability project. London School for Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, London UK.
- Tong A, Sainsbury P and Craig J (2007). Consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative research (COREQ): A 32-item checklist for interviews and focus groups. *Int. J. Qual. Health Care*, **19**: 349-357.
- Weeks SA and Lehmann D (2008). The effect of passive smoking on the risk of otitis media in Aboriginal and non-Aboriginal children in the Kalgoorlie-Boulder region of Western Australia. *Med. J.*, **188**(10): 599-603.
- World Health Organization (1989). Strengthening the performance of community health workers in primary health care. Geneva: World Health Organization, Report No: 780.
- Yeung-Yue KA, Brentjens MH, Lee PC and Tying SK (2002). Herpes simplex viruses 1 and 2. *Dermatol. Clin.*, **20**(2): 249-266.